

Social media
report 2024

This social media and web report visually summarizes data extracted from the CNR-INO social media over the last year (January 2024 - December 2024).

The report highlights strengths and weaknesses in the CNR-INO communication strategy and offers useful insight to identify the audience, monitor engagement and schedule targeted contents.

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Italy (86,8%) - France - Greece - Spain - United States -
Mexico - Egypt - United Kingdom - Germany - Brazil

Top countries

Audience

Demographics

Trends

Potential audience

Followers ●

Lifetime

1,133

Age & gender ●

Top towns/cities

Top countries

Demographics

Followers

1133

Posts

206

Shares

253

Post
engagement

1635

Views

15.2K

Reach

24.1K

Content
interactions

1.8K

Watch time

2h 27m

100% from organic

Top contents

Top content formats

Published content

Based on up to 200 pieces of content

-12.9% vs 31 Dec 2022 – 31 Dec 2023

Photos
109

Links
16

Videos
6

Reels
3

Text
1

Stories
0

Facebook reach

+24.0% vs 31 Dec 2022 – 31 Dec 2023

Photos
11,913

Others
9,464

Multi-photo
7,964

Links
2,066

Videos
979

Reels
202

Text
164

Content interactions

-31.4% vs 31 Dec 2022 – 31 Dec 2023

Photos
927

Multi-photo
602

Links
223

Others
28

Videos
27

Reels
16

Stories
5

Top content by views

Boost content

See all content

I nostri ricercatori stanno partecipando...

1 November 10:10

2.2K views, 66 likes, 2 shares

Questa mattina, a Futuro Remoto a...

19 October 08:20

1.2K views, 42 likes, 0 shares

#CNRINONews ✨🏆 Marco Bellini awarde...

26 November 02:49

1.2K views, 25 likes, 2 shares

[IT] La tradizione della Christmas Lecture...

14 December 06:36

1K views, 17 likes, 3 shares

L' Istituto Nazionale c Ottica del CNR sarà..

24 October 07:30

781 views, 23 likes, 3 shares

Top posts per “Reach”

Title		Date published ↑↓	Reach ⓘ ↓	Likes and reactions ⓘ ↑↓	Comments ⓘ ↑↓	Shares ⓘ ↑↓
Oggi l'Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle R... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	12 Jun 2024	6.8K	42	0	11
Avete mai sentito parlare della tela di Gebelein? Si trova al Museo Egi... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	21 Mar 2024	4.9K	18	0	15
Martedì 1 ottobre non perdere l'evento al @cnrsocial a Roma per cele... Photo · cnr_ino	Boost	30 Sep 2024	2K	34	1	4
I nostri ricercatori stanno partecipando a eventi di divulgazione scient... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	1 Nov 2024	1.1K	25	1	3
It's time for the global scientific community to recognize and support ... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	11 Feb 2024	955	15	0	9
Domani martedì 9 aprile al Museo di Fisica del Centro Musei delle Sci... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	8 Apr 2024	850	12	0	10
#CNRINONews 🏆 Marco Bellini awarded the International Prize "Pr... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	26 Nov 2024	788	17	2	1
#bando per imprese e organismi di ricerca L'ecosistema regionale tos... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	2 Jan 2024	721	2	0	8
#daguerreotypes are 19th-century photographic images on metallic ... Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR	Boost	7 May 2024	676	10	0	1
Simposio CNR INO 2024 #CNRINO Story · cnr_ino	Boost	28 Nov 2024	584	3	--	0

Top posts per “Shares”

Title	Date published ↑↓	Reach ⓘ ↑↓	Likes and reactions ⓘ ↑↓	Comments ⓘ ↑↓	Shares ⓘ ↓
Avete mai sentito parlare della tela di Gebelein? Si trova al Museo Egizio... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	21 Mar 2024	4.9K	18	0	15
Oggi l'Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle Ric... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	12 Jun 2024	6.8K	42	0	11
Domani martedì 9 aprile al Museo di Fisica del Centro Musei delle Scien... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	8 Apr 2024	850	12	0	10
It's time for the global scientific community to recognize and support #... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	11 Feb 2024	955	15	0	9
#bando per imprese e organismi di ricerca L'ecosistema regionale toska... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	2 Jan 2024	721	2	0	8
Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR oggi a #Napoli per discutere dell'int... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	7 Jun 2024	197	9	1	7
[IT] La tradizione della Christmas Lecture dell'INO si rinnova Venerdì 20... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	14 Dec 2024	572	4	0	6
Vuoi sapere di più sull'utilizzo di tecniche diagnostiche non-invasive pe... <small>Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	16 May 2024	474	8	0	5
Lunedì 15 Aprile si terrà a Napoli la celebrazione del World Quantum Da... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	12 Apr 2024	539	7	0	5
Venerdì 9 febbraio, Napoli ospiterà il secondo incontro del #pcto "Mi... <small>Photo · Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR</small>	7 Feb 2024	428	8	0	5

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

22,9%

New followers

Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del CNR

Export Data

1 Jan 2022-31 Dec 2022

All content

Ads, Posts and Stories

Recent content ↑↓	Type	Reach ⓘ ↑↓	Likes and reacti... ⓘ ↑	Sticker taps ⓘ ↑↓	Replies ⓘ ↑↓	Link clicks ⓘ ↑↓	Comr
#jobopportunity at University of ... 8 Jan 2022	Post	Boost post	78	0	--	--	--
#PhDopportunity at @amolfopen... 16 Jan 2022	Post	Boost post	76	0	--	--	2
#CallForPapers on #quantum ima... 27 Jan 2022	Post	Boost post	77	0	--	--	2
#ItalianQuantumWeeks a Trieste! ... 30 Mar 2022	Post	Boost post	64	0	--	--	1
#CallForPapers Fino al 3 aprile... 30 Mar 2022	Post	Boost Unavailable	82	0	--	--	--
Don't miss the #opportunity to ... 3 May 2022	Post	Boost post	74	0	--	--	--
#PhD opportunity in Technologie... 3 May 2022	Post	Boost Unavailable	90	0	--	--	--

Most engaging posts

22,3%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

Age & gender

Top towns/cities

Top countries

Demographics

Top countries

Followers

473

Posts

91

Views

9.5K

Reach

5.4K

Content
interactions

285

Visits

9,5K

New Followers

+79

Unfollows

-21

Potential audience

Top contents

 Top content by views

[Boost content](#) [See all content](#)

Martedì 1 ottobre non perdere l'evento al...

30 September 10:38

👁 2.5K ❤️ 34

🗨 1 ➡ 4

Simposio CNR INO 2024 #CNRINO

28 November 02:36

👁 645 ❤️ 3

🗨 0 ➡ 0

I nostri ricercatori stanno partecipando...

1 November 10:12

👁 508 ❤️ 21

🗨 2 ➡ 1

Suggerimenti dalla mostra "Co-vision. T...

20 October 09:21

👁 488 ❤️ 15

🗨 0 ➡ 2

#STREETSERN24 🌟

Torna anche...

26 September 02:18

👁 449 ❤️ 5

🗨 0 ➡ 2

 Top posts by interactions

[Boost content](#) [See all content](#)

Oggi, 30 aprile 2024, a 25 anni dalla firma...

30 April 07:47

🗨 142 ❤️ 140

🗨 1 ➡ 1

Martedì 1 ottobre non perdere l'evento al...

30 September 10:38

🗨 43 ❤️ 34

🗨 1 ➡ 4

Incredible breakthrough in the...

24 May 02:17

🗨 27 ❤️ 24

🗨 1 ➡ 1

I nostri ricercatori stanno partecipando...

1 November 10:12

🗨 24 ❤️ 21

🗨 2 ➡ 1

🌟 #CNRINONews

Siamo felici di...

26 November 03:27

🗨 21 ❤️ 20

🗨 0 ➡ 1

Followers

703

Posts

91

Shares

100

Impressions

17K

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

40,4%

New followers

CNR Istituto Nazionale di Ottica @CNR_INO · Jun 12, 2024

Oggi l'Istituto Nazionale di Ottica del [@CNRsocial_](#) dedica la sua aula didattica a Fortunato Tito [#Arecchi](#), suo storico direttore, professore di fisica all'[@UNI_FIRENZE](#), pioniere nel campo dei [#laser](#) e dell'ottica quantistica.

↻ 3

♥ 7

📊 740

Top post

16,8%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

March 2024 - Dec 2024

Italy - France - India - United Kingdom - Spain - Germany - Belgium - Portugal -
Egypt - Turkey - Switzerzland - Iran - Denmark - Netherlands - Greece ...

Top countries

Followers

1778

Posts

296

Shares

29

Impressions

78.5K

Reactions

1.4K

Comments

26

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

74,1%

+1317

New followers

CNR-INO

1,778 followers

3mo · 🌐

#CNRINONews

Marco Bellini awarded the International Prize "Prof. Luigi Tartufari".

We are pleased to announce that Marco Bellini, research director at the ...more

🌐 Jana Striova and 51 others

4 comments · 1 repost

Like

Comment

Repost

Comment as CNR-INO...

Most relevant ▾

Luca Salasnich · 2nd

3mo ...

Full Professor of Theoretical Physics at Università degli Studi di Padova

Congratulazioni! Alcuni lavori di Marco Bellini sono veramente eccezionali!!!

Show translation

Like | Reply

Chiara Mustarelli · 2nd

3mo ...

CTER at CNR

Complimenti Marco!!!

Show translation

Like | Reply

Angela Pirri · 2nd

(edited) 3mo ...

Senior researcher in Physics

Congratulations Marco!

Like | Reply

Leonardo Fallani · 2nd

3mo ...

Professor in Physics at University of Florence, specialized in quantum ...

Congratulations Marco!!

Like | Reply

Top post

1,6%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

Watching countries

Italy

Followers

96

Posts

2

Impressions

5.9K

Page views

460

-62%

Visualization time

38,2 hour -56%

Average visualization time

4:58 min

93 visualization
27,1 hour visualization
795 impressions
3 likes

Top video

New followers

Comparing some data

Location

Facebook

Male 51,6% Female 48,4%

Instagram

Male 47,1% Female 52,9%

Linkedin

Senior 33,9%, entry 32,1%, training 8%

Twitter

no data available

Website

no data available

Youtube

no data available

User's identikit

Facebook

1133

Instagram

473

Twitter

703

Linkedin

1778

Youtube

96

Users: numbers

+1911 new followers
on social media
in the last year

Facebook

22,9%

Twitter

40,3%

Linkedin

74%

Youtube

33,3%

Audience Grow Rate Percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

Facebook

22,3%

Linkedin

1,6%

Twitter

16,8%

Youtube

0%

Amplification Rate Percentage

It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks

(Avinash Kaushik, Google)

In 2025 we opened a new
social media account:
BlueSky

@cnr-ino.bsky.social

CNR-INO Social Media Report 2024
Author and graphics: Laura Benassi
Published in March 2025